

Two Different and Equal Coefficients of Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: Nowadays, the growing complexity of mathematical and computational modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical and combinatorial equations for solving today's scientific problems and challenges. This paper presents the two different and equal coefficients of combinatorial geometric series with detailed proof. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to compute the multiple summations of a geometric series [1-9], a new idea stimulated his mind to create a new type of geometric series. As a result, a combinatorial geometric series was developed with new idea of binomial coefficients. The computation of combinatorial geometric series and its properties and applications are explained in the next section.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [10-19] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

By substituting $x = 1$ in the combinatorial geometric series $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$, we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r (1)^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r = V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1} \text{ and}$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r = V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{n-2}^r + V_{n-1}^r = V_{n-1}^{r+1}$$

From these two binomial identities, we get the following result:

$$V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}.$$

3. Two Different and Equal Binomial Coefficients

V_r^n and V_n^r are two different and equal binomial coefficients, i. e. $V_r^n = V_n^r$.

Let prove the binomial identity $V_r^n = V_n^r$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Proof. } V_r^n = V_n^r &\Rightarrow \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\cdots(r+n)}{n!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+r)}{r!} \\ &\Rightarrow r!(r+1)(r+2)\cdots(r+n) = n!(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+r) \\ &\Rightarrow (n+r)! = (n+r)!. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, it is proved.

4. Conclusion

In this article, computation of the summation of binomial series and combinatorial geometric series and also its theorems, lemmas, and corollaries were developed using the basic mathematical and numerical techniques. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real world problems.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation and Calculus for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Identities and Expansions. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(7), 14648–01i. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss7pp14648-01i>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2022) Application of Factorial and Binomial identities in Information, Cybersecurity and Machine Learning. *International Journal of Advanced Networking and Applications*, 14(1), 5258-5260. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-pnx53-v21>.
- [3] Annamalai, C. (2022) Combinatorial and Multinomial Coefficients and its Computing Techniques for Machine Learning and Cybersecurity. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(8), 14713–01i. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss8pp14713-01i>.
- [4] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation of Multinomial and Factorial Theorems for Cryptography and Machine Learning. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks-v9>.
- [5] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation of Binomial, Factorial and Multinomial Theorems for Machine Learning and Cybersecurity. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks-v11>.
- [6] Annamalai, C. (2022) Series and Summations on Binomial Coefficients of Optimized Combination. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 8(3), 14123-01e. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl8iss3pp14123-01e>.
- [7] Annamalai, C. (2022) Factorials and Integers for Applications in Computing and Cryptography. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-b6mks>.

- [8] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computing Method for Combinatorial Geometric Series and Binomial Expansion. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4168016>.
- [9] Annamalai, C. (2022) Annamalai's Binomial Identity and Theorem, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4097907>.
- [10] Annamalai, C. (2010) Applications of exponential decay and geometric series in effective medicine dosage. *Advances in Bioscience and Biotechnology*, 1(1), 51-54. <https://doi.org/10.4236/abb.2010.11008>.
- [11] Annamalai, C. (2017) Analysis and Modelling of Annamalai Computing Geometric Series and Summability. *Mathematical Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences*, 6(1), 11-15. <https://doi.org/10.15415/mjis.2017.61002>.
- [12] Annamalai, C. (2017) Annamalai Computing Method for Formation of Geometric Series using in Science and Technology. *International Journal for Science and Advance Research In Technology*, 3(8), 187-289. <http://ijsart.com/Home/IssueDetail/17257>.
- [13] Annamalai, C. (2017) Computational modelling for the formation of geometric series using Annamalai computing method. *Jñānābha*, 47(2), 327-330. <https://zbmath.org/?q=an%3A1391.65005>.
- [14] Annamalai, C. (2018) Novel Computation of Algorithmic Geometric Series and Summability. *Journal of Algorithms and Computation*, 50(1), 151-153. <https://www.doi.org/10.22059/JAC.2018.68866>.
- [15] Annamalai, C. (2020) Combinatorial Technique for Optimizing the combination. *The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences*, 6(2), 0189-0192. <https://doi.org/10.18540/jcecvl6iss2pp0189-0192>.
- [16] Annamalai, C. (2018) Annamalai's Computing Model for Algorithmic Geometric Series and Its Mathematical Structures. *Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 3(1),1-6 <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.mcs.20180301.11>.
- [17] Annamalai, C. (2018) Algorithmic Computation of Annamalai's Geometric Series and Summability. *Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 3(5),100-101. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.mcs.20180305.11>.
- [16] Annamalai, C. (2019) Recursive Computations and Differential and Integral Equations for Summability of Binomial Coefficients with Combinatorial Expressions. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Mechanical and Materials Engineering*, 4(1), 6-10. <https://ijsrmme.com/IJSRMME19362>.
- [19] Annamalai, C. (2022) Computation for the Summation of Binomial Series and Combinatorial Geometric Series. *COE, Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.33774/coe-2022-0q625-v4>.